

C5.2 - Briefing

Thanks again for your interest in participating in the experiment.

For while you only have to answer this small questionnaire. It might take less than 1 minute.

There are 3 questions in this survey.

Briefing

How many years of professional experience in software engineering do you have? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- Less than 5 years
 5 years or more

Does your professional experience include requirements elicitation? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- Yes
 No / Insignificant

To which role do you relate most of your professional experience? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- Requirements Engineer
 UX Designer
 Business Analyst
 Architect
 Developer
 Quality Assurance
 Other

Thank you!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.